

INTERLINEAR TRANSLATION

ACROSS THE MUSLIM WORLD

A Comparative Perspective

Themed Section

edited by

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Not the Utawi You Think You Know: Some Preliminary Notes on Early Javanese Interlinear Translations

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Abstract

This article explores the historical trajectory of the Javanese word *utawi* within the tradition of interlinear translation of Arabic Islamic texts from the 16th to the 19th century. While in contemporary usage—particularly within *pesantren* communities where this translation practice has largely survived—*utawi* serves as a marker of the *mubtada'* (subject) in nominal sentences, earlier evidence reveals a more layered history. Based on close philological analysis of manuscripts, the study demonstrates that in the 16th and 17th centuries *utawi* was primarily employed to render the *wāw al-isti'nāf*, an Arabic particle that signals the beginning of a new sentence or clause. Only gradually, especially during the 18th century, did *utawi* become stabilized as a marker of the *mubtada'*, a pattern that continued into the 19th century and even today. This diachronic shift highlights not only the changing role of a single lexical item but also broader pedagogical and linguistic transformations in the Javanese Islamic tradition. By tracing these developments, the article contributes to a more precise understanding of the internal mechanics of interlinear translation and proposes that patterns of *utawi* usage can serve as valuable indicators for the dating of otherwise anonymous manuscripts. Ultimately, this study situates *utawi* as both a linguistic key and a historical witness to the intellectual practices that shaped Islamic learning in Java.

Keywords: *utawi*, Arabic-Javanese interlinear translation, *pesantren*, Islamic manuscript culture, *mubtada'*, *wāw al-isti'nāf*.

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Introduction

One of the most striking features of early Islamic literature in Java is its systematic use of interlinear translation, a pedagogical and commentarial method that allowed readers to access Arabic religious texts through the local language, Javanese. Within this system, certain words functioned as grammatical and discursive markers, guiding readers through the syntactic and semantic structure of the source text. Among these, the word *utawi*, the focus of this article, stands out for its consistent presence and evolving role across manuscripts from the 16th century until today. While *utawi* is most commonly known today as an indicator of the subject of a nominal Arabic sentence (*mubtada'*), its historical usage suggests a more complex trajectory that deserves closer examination.

Despite the abundance of scholarship on Javanese literature and Islamic manuscript traditions, few studies have addressed the grammatical mechanics of interlinear translation, and even fewer have examined the diachronic development of specific translation devices like *utawi*. Existing works tend to focus either on the content of these manuscripts or on broader questions of Islamization and textual transmission.² While pioneering scholars have provided invaluable insights into the literary and historical contexts of Javanese Islamic texts,³ they did not delve into the microstructure of translation practices. The internal linguistic system these texts employ remains largely underexplored, leaving open the question of how specific grammatical markers emerged, stabilized, or shifted in meaning and function over time.

Before proceeding further, a brief introduction of the system of interlinear translation practiced in Java merits attention here. Among the communities that employ it—most notably the *pesantren* (Islamic boarding school) milieu—this system is often referred to as the “*utawi-iki-iku* translation system.” The use of *utawi-iki-iku* as a shorthand for *pesantren* interlinear translation system likely stems from the frequent appearance of these three words, particularly in the translation of chapter titles in classical texts. The classical books studied in *pesantren* are typically divided into chapters, each introduced by a simple phrase such as *bāb al-ṭahāra* (chapter on purification) or *bāb al-bay'* (chapter on trade). To translate these chapter titles, *pesantren* scholars developed a complex grammatical analysis and rendered that analysis into Javanese.

2 Merle C. Ricklefs, *Mystic Synthesis in Java: A History of Islamization from the Fourteenth to the Early Nineteenth Centuries* (East Bridge, 2006); G.W.J. Drewes, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari: A 16th Century Javanese Muslim Text Attributed to the Saint of Bonan Re-Edited and Translated with an Introduction* (Springer Netherlands, 1969); Azyumardi Azra, *Jaringan Ulama: Timur Tengah dan Kepulauan Nusantara Abad XVII Dan XVIII: Melacak Akar-Akar Pembaruan Pemikiran Islam di Indonesia* (Mizan, 1994).

3 See, for example, G.W.J. Drewes, *Een Javaanse Primbon: Uit De Zestiende Eeuw Opnieuw Uitgegeven En Vertaald* (Brill, 1954); G.W.J. Drewes and L.F. Brakel, *The Poems of Hamzah Fansuri* (Foris Publication, 1986); Nancy K. Florida, *Writing the Past, Inscripting the Future* (Duke University Press, 1995); Merle C. Ricklefs, *The Seen and Unseen Worlds in Java, 1726–1749: History, Literature and Islam in the Court of Pakubuwana II* (University of Hawai'i Press, 1998); Ronit Ricci, *Islam Translated: Literature, Conversion, and the Arabic Cosmopolis of South and Southeast Asia* (University of Chicago Press, 2011).

Written Arabic original	<i>bāb al-ṣalā</i>
Grammatically analyzed	<i>[hādhā] bāb [fī bayān] al-ṣalā</i>
Utawi-iki-iku translation	<i>[utawi iki iku] bab [ingdalem nerangaken] ṣalāt</i>
English translation	[utawi this is] a chapter [on explaining] prayer

Table 1 Translation of an Arabic chapter title with *utawi-iki-iku* system

Upon grammatical analysis, *bāb al-ṣalā* is understood as a shortened form of *hādhā bāb fī bayān al-ṣalā* (this is a chapter explaining purification), where *hādhā* functions as the *mubtada'* (subject) and *bāb* as the *khobar* (predicate). In modern pesantren interlinear translation, *mubtada'* and *khobar* are typically rendered with *utawi* and *iku*, respectively, resulting in a full translation of *bāb al-ṣalā* as *utawi iki iku bab ingdalem nerangaken ṣalāt* (*utawi* this is a chapter on explaining prayer).⁴ This analytical approach is applied not only to chapter titles but also to any phrase requiring similar treatment, making *utawi-iki-iku* so common that it has come to represent the distinctive translation system of pesantren.

Fig. 1 An interlinear translation of an Arabic phrase into Javanese using the *utawi-iki-iku* system

Studies such as those by Sidney Jones and Aly Basalamah have tried to provide a sort of introduction to the system.⁵ They indicate that by the 20th century, Javanese Muslims had developed a distinct system to interlinearly translate Arabic textbooks. One key feature of this system, as Basalamah describes it, is a form of “*bahasa simbolik*” (symbolic language)

4 *Utawi* is left untranslated here and kept at the beginning of the sentence to reflect its position in the original Javanese text, while the rest of the sentence has English equivalents, including “is” for *iku*.
 5 Sidney Jones, “Arabic Instruction and Literacy in Javanese Muslim Schools,” *International Journal of Society and Language* 42 (1983): 83–94; Aly Abubakar Basalamah, “Memahami Kitab Kuning Melalui Terjemahan Tradisional: Suatu Pendekatan Tradisional Terjemahan Pondok Pesantren,” *Al-Jami’ah* 55 (1994): 61–69.

that encodes grammatical positions, morphemic changes, and other linguistic elements, including words like *utawi*. Beyond *utawi*, the system developed symbols to indicate a wide range of grammatical (*naḥw*) statuses—such as *ing* for *maf'ūl bih* (object) and *apane* for *tamyīz* (a specifier)—as well as several other aspects, including morphology (*ṣarf*), particularly in marking past (*māḍī*) and future (*mustaqbal*) tenses when they need to be explicitly shown.⁶ Interlinear translation practices in pesantren served a dual purpose: they facilitated both the study of the textbook's content and the learning of Arabic itself. As neither Jones nor Basalamah focuses on any particular pesantren as a case study, their research implies that this interlinear translation system had become a widely recognized convention across Javanese-speaking regions. Building on the research of Jones and Basalamah and connecting it with what I have observed in the interlinear translation practices in pesantren, I believe that Javanese Muslims, particularly those in pesantren communities, have taken for granted that this system has been a long-established convention, not only in the present but even in centuries past.

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This study aims to fill part of that gap, namely the lack of detailed analysis of the internal linguistic mechanics of Javanese interlinear translation and their historical development, and to challenge that taken-for-granted approach to the Javanese interlinear translation system. In doing so the study traces the historical trajectory of *utawi* as it appears mainly in a corpus of interlinear Javanese translations of Arabic texts dated between the 16th and 19th centuries. It draws on close philological analysis of selected manuscripts from pesantren collections and public archives, examining not only the appearance of *utawi* but also its syntactic environments and co-occurrence with other translation markers. The investigation is guided by a diachronic framework, allowing for the identification of gradual shifts, ruptures, and moments of stabilization in translation practice.

Throughout this article I argue that the function of *utawi* shifted over time—initially serving to render the Arabic conjunction *wāw al-isti'nāf* (a type of *wāw*, “and”, that starts a new, independent sentence or clause) and later becoming stabilized as a marker of the *mubtada'*.⁷ This analysis relies on both dated and undated manuscripts, with the aim of establishing not only patterns of linguistic change but also potential implications for dating anonymous texts. By doing so, I aim to provide new insights into the evolution of the Javanese interlinear tradition, demonstrating how the changing role of *utawi* reflects broader pedagogical and linguistic transformations in Islamic Java. Ultimately, this micro-level focus contributes to a more nuanced understanding of textual transmission, local hermeneutics, and the historical development of Islamic education in the region.

6 Saiful Umam, “Localizing Islamic Orthodoxy in Northern Coastal Java in the Late 19th and Early 20th Centuries: A Study of Pegon Islamic Texts” (PhD Dissertation, University of Hawai'i, 2011). Following on Umam's footsteps, Muhammad Jaeni and Sahal Mahfudh provide a more detailed and comprehensive discussion of this system. See Muhammad Jaeni, “Pola-Pola Pengapsahan Kitab Pesantren Kiai Pesisir Utara Jawa Tengah Abad XIX-XX: Kajian Histori-Sosiolinguistik” (UIN Walisongo, 2019); Sahal Mahfudh, “Al-Kitāba al-'Arabiyya Li-Lughat al-Jāwiyyah (Pegon): Dirāsa Lughawiyya Ijtīmā'iyya 'alā -Sībqā'ihā Fī Mujtama' al-Besantren al-Taqlīdī Bi-Jāwā” (UIN Sunan Kalijaga, 2023).

7 It is important to note that a *mubtada'* refers only to the subject of a nominal sentence. The subject of a verbal sentence is called a *fā'il* (literally “the doer,” or “the one who performs an action”).

Utawi (اتاوِي or اتاو)

Gericke and Roorda explain that *utawi* is a refined form of *atawa* or *utawa*.⁸ In Javanese, this word functions as a “conjunction that links what follows to what precedes it, [presenting it as an alternative or] as something else” and serves as a counterpart to Dutch words such as *of* (or), *en/of anders* (and/or otherwise), *als ook* (as well), and *ook* (also).⁹ Elsewhere, Gericke and Roorda also note that Javanese speakers do not always use *utawi* in this sense.¹⁰ In other words, Javanese speakers express such conjunctive meanings with alternative forms and use *atawa-utawa-utawi* more flexibly to express additional meanings.

The word *utawi* is used very frequently in two manuscripts known to date as the earliest witnesses of Arabic-Javanese interlinear translation practices. Purchased by Jan Theunisz (d. 1638) in the Netherlands around 1610 and now kept in the library of the University of Amsterdam, I F 31 and I H 1 recorded the appearance of *utawi* more than a hundred times.¹¹ In all these instances, I found that *utawi* is used in translations of words that are preceded by the Arabic particle *wāw*, known in Arabic grammar as *wāw al-isti'nāf*.¹² As an introduction to a new sentence, what follows it might be a nominal sentence (*jumla ismiyya*) or a verbal one (*jumla fi'liyya*). In the case of a nominal sentence, the first word following the *wāw* is the *mubtada'* and can only be a noun (*ism*) or a word that acts as a noun (similar to the English infinitive). With this in mind, and considering the modern understanding of *utawi* in the *utawi-iku* system as rendering the *mubtada'* status, the clearest examples supporting my

8 It is interesting to note that *utawi* is one of very few words, if not the only one from the *krama* (refined) register used as grammatical indicators in the *utawi-iki-iku* translation system.

9 Johann F.C. Gericke and Taco Roorda, *Javaansch-Nederlandsch Handwoordenboek* (Brill, 1901), 1:86.

10 Johann F.C. Gericke and Taco Roorda, *Javaansch-Nederduitsch Woordenboek* (Johannes Müller, 1847), 33.

11 Although often attested as the earliest Javanese interlinear manuscripts, the two manuscripts have enjoyed very little attention from scholars. To the best of my knowledge, only Nur Ahmad has revisited these two manuscripts in a few short essays of his. His writings on these manuscripts were initially published around 2017 as popular essays on the Islamic website www.alif.id. In 2020, they were compiled into a book titled *Wajah Islam Nusantara: Jejak Tradisi Santri, Aksara Pegon, dan Keberislaman dalam Manuskrip Kuno* (Tangerang: Pustaka Compass, 2020). However, his analysis remains limited to the translation of two Arabic words, which he argues are uniquely adapted to the local linguistic context, without delving further into the manuscripts themselves. The two words in question are *siwāk*, which is translated as *susur* (betel chewing?), and *safar*, which is translated as *pelayaran* (sailing). Ahmad then connects both terms to the socio-cultural context of Javanese society, which was familiar with both betel chewing and seafaring. For further discussion, see <https://jangkah.id/2024/01/11/islam-akses-literasi-dan-pribumisasi-pelajaran-dari-dua-manuskrip-kitab-fikih-dengan-terjemah-pegon-jawa-tahun-1610-m/>, accessed in March 2025. It is worth noting that Ahmad draws these examples only from the translation practices found in the *Kitab al-Īdāh* (cataloged as I H 1). For more about I F 31 and I H 1, see also Hendrik Frederik Wijnman, “De Hebraëcus Jan Theunisz Barbarossius Alias Johannes Antonides Als Lector in Het Arabisch Aan de Leidse Universiteit (1612/1613). Een Hoofdstuk Amsterdamse Geleerdengeschiedenis,” *Studia Rosenthaliana* 2, no. 2 (1968): 22–23.

12 I follow Dror’s translation of Bābitī’s definition of *wāw al-isti'nāf*. She writes that “*wāw l-isti'nāf* is used as a particle with which a speech begins, [or] the sentence that followed it is completely independent in meaning from the sentence that precedes it.” Yehudit Dror, “Is Each Particle in the Qur’ān Translatable? The Case of Wāw al-Isti’nāf Preceding the Fawāṣil,” *Babel* 61, no. 1 (2015): 24.

argument are cases where *utawi* is followed by a word that is not a noun or noun-like, i.e., *fi'l* (verb) or *ḥarf*.¹³

Such examples are not uncommon in both of these texts. In I F 31, we encounter *wa-yajūzu* (and it is allowed), which is translated as *utawi wenang* (*utawi* is allowed) (Fig. 1). Since *yajūzu* is a verb, it cannot directly serve as a *mubtada'* unless it is either nominalized (e.g., *jawāz*) or introduced by a particle such as *an*, forming *an yajūza*. In this case, *yajūzu* appears directly after the *wāw* (*wa-yajūzu*), which means the word—*yajūzu*—cannot function as a *mubtada'*. Yet it is translated as *utawi wenang*. This raises a problem: since *wenang* corresponds to *yajūzu*, it is unlikely that *utawi* is translating the *mubtada'*. Instead, it seems that *utawi* is being used to render the particle *wa*.

Fig. 2 *Al-Ghāya wa-l-Taqrīb*, Library of the University of Amsterdam, I F 1, fol. 34. A *wāw*-rendering *utawi* is followed by the verb *yajūzu* (*wenang*, “is allowed”).

The *isti'nāf* function of the *wāw* is especially important in Arabic, which doesn't use punctuation marks like periods, commas, or others to indicate the position of words, phrases, or sentences within a text. To clarify the *isti'nāf* function of *wāw*, I will provide a more complete context of the sentence from this example.

Wa-ṣalātu l-jamā'ati sunnatun mu'akkad. [sic.] Wa-yajibu 'alā l-ma'mūmi an yanwiyā l-jamā'ata dūna l-imāmi. Wa-yajūzu an ya'tamma al-ḥurru bi-l-'abdi.

Congregational prayer is a *sunna mu'akkad* (highly emphasized practice/tradition). A *ma'mūm* (congregant) is required to have an intention (*niyya*) to join the congregation, but the *imām* (prayer leader) is not. A free person is allowed to become a *ma'mūm* (congregant) of a slave.¹⁴

In this “paragraph” the *wāw* does not function as a conjunction but rather marks the beginning of a new sentence. This role is similar to that of, in English, a capital letter after a period, which signals the end of the previous sentence. When encountering a period, a reader

13 Finding an exact English equivalent for *ḥarf* is quite challenging—if one exists at all. In Arabic grammar, *ḥarf* is part of the tripartite division of parts of speech, alongside *ism* and *fi'l*. While *ism* is commonly equated with “noun” and *fi'l* with “verb,” *ḥarf* is almost always defined in negative terms. Sibawayh, one of the foundational figures in Arabic grammatical theory, describes *ḥarf* as “that which conveys a meaning but is neither a noun nor a verb” (*jā'a li-ma'nān laysa bi-sm wa-lā fi'l*) Sibawayh, *Al-Kiṭāb* (Maktaba al-Khānjī, 1988), 1:12. As such, *ḥarf* encompasses a wide range of categories that, in English grammar, would be distributed across distinct parts of speech—namely, prepositions, conjunctions, and particles.

14 I F 31, fols. 33–34

immediately knows that the sentence they are reading has ended, and what follows is the start of a new sentence. Similarly, when encountering wāw al-isti'nāf, a reader immediately knows that they are facing a new sentence, and the previous one has concluded.

In I H 1, we encounter another case, when *wa-idhā* (and when/if) is translated as *utawi tatkala* (*utawi* when/if) (Fig. 2). This is an even stronger example because *idhā* is a conditional particle (*adāt al-sharṭ*), so there is no way the particle can serve as a *mubtada'* in a sentence. However, the interlinear translation uses *utawi tatkala*. Using the same logic as before, we can identify *tatkala* as rendering *idhā*, and once again, *utawi* is translating the particle *wa*. The function of *isti'nāf* in this example is also easier to recognize because it is the first sentence in a new *kitāb* (literally “book,” but used here in the sense of “chapter”).

Fig. 3 *Al-Īdāh*, Library of the University of Amsterdam, I H 1, fol. 13. A *wāw*-rendering *utawi* is followed by the conditional particle *idhā* (*tatkala* [when/if]).

The only instance of *utawi* that clearly represents the position of the *mubtada'*—as it does in modern usage—is in the phrase *kullu mā'in* (all kinds of water) on fol. 2 of I H 1 (Fig. 3). This word begins the first sentence of a new *kitāb*, does not have *wāw al-isti'nāf*, but is translated with *utawi*. Apart from this example, *utawi* is always used to translate the *isti'nāf* function of *wāw*.

Fig. 4 *Al-Īdāh*, Library of the University of Amsterdam, I H 1, fol. 2. The only *utawi* to function as indicating the *mubtada'* status.

The use of *utawi* to render a *mubtada'* that is not preceded by *wāw al-isti'nāf* appears more frequently in Sloane 2645 from the British Library collection, a copy of *al-Muqaddima al-*

Ḥaḍrāmiyya (The Ḥaḍrami Introduction or Prolegomenon).¹⁵ However, this usage consistently occurs at the beginning of a new *faṣl* (section), specifically in the translation of its first word. Within the main body of a *faṣl*, *mubtada*'s that lack *wāw al-isti'nāf* are almost never translated with *utawi*. Notably, there is also a *faṣl* whose first sentence begins with a verb (*fi'l*) and lacks *wāw al-isti'nāf*, but is still translated with *utawi* (Fig. 4). While this might be seen as an error, it is also possible that the translator of Sloane 2645 was so accustomed to encountering the formula *wāw al-isti'nāf* + *fi'l* at the beginning of a *faṣl*, and thus inserted *utawi* out of habit. In any case, I would argue that Sloane 2645 reflects a broader pattern in which *utawi* is predominantly used to translate *wāw al-isti'nāf*.

Fig. 5 *Al-Muqaddima al-Ḥaḍrāmiyya*, British Museum Library, Sloane 2645, fol. 75v. The use of *utawi* in translating *fi'l* without *wāw al-isti'nāf*.

Alongside the general patterns outlined above, the three earliest manuscripts (I F 31 and I H 1 from University of Amsterdam and Sloane 2645 from British Library) also present exceptions in the use of *utawi* and in the translation of words that either contain *wāw al-isti'nāf* or function grammatically as *mubtada*'. The pronouns *huwa* (he) and *hiya* (she), when occupying the syntactic position of the *mubtada*', are consistently rendered formulaically as *iya iku* (it is). When preceded by *wāw*—whether as *isti'nāf* or simple conjunction—the phrase is not introduced by *utawi*, but by *lan* (and), resulting in *lan iya iku* (and it is). Conversely, *utawi* is consistently absent when the *mubtada*' is preceded not by *wāw al-isti'nāf* but by *fā'* *al-isti'nāf*.¹⁶ In such cases, it is either replaced by *maka* (then) or omitted altogether. A similar pattern can be observed in the translation of *wa-ammā* (and, as for) and *fa-ammā* (then, as

15 Sloane 2645 is a copy and translation of a legal treatise authored by 'Abdullāh b. 'Abd al-Raḥmān Bā Faḍl (d. 1512) of Ḥaḍramawt, Yemen—hence its title, *al-Muqaddima al-Ḥaḍrāmiyya*. It was copied (and possibly also translated) by a scribe named 'Abd al-Qaḍīm. The colophon records the date as 1545 in the Javanese calendar—an Islamized adaptation of the lunar Indic Saka calendar—corresponding to 1623/4 AD. While there is no clear record of how the manuscript came into the hands of the British scholar and collector Sir Hans Sloane (d. 1753), it was most likely acquired through trade. For further information on the Sloane collection, see Annabel Teh Gallop, "Southeast Asian Manuscripts from the Collection of Sir Hans Sloane in the British Library," *Wacana* 20, no. 1 (2019): 15–31. For details on the Javanese calendar, see Ian Proudfoot, *Old Muslim Calendars of Southeast Asia* (Brill, 2006).

16 Besides *wāw*, *fā'* can also function as *isti'nāf*, that is "when *fa-* is taken as beginning a new utterance, unconnected to the preceding one." For more, see Arik Sadan, *The Subjunctive Mood in Arabic Grammatical Thought* (Brill, 2012), 152.

for): the former is regularly rendered as *utawi anapun*, while the latter appears as either *maka anapun* or simply *anapun*.

This usage of *utawi* to render the *wāw* in its function as an *isti'nāf* particle can also be observed in other early Islamic manuscripts, including *Pegon* manuscripts not composed in interlinear format as well as texts written in Javanese script. By contrast, the alternative function of *utawi*—namely, its role in marking the *mubtada'*—along with the exceptional uses outlined above, appears to be limited to a narrower corpus of interlinear works.¹⁷ One such example is the manuscript from the Leiden University Library, cataloged as Or. 5716. This manuscript contains several texts, one of which is a translation of *al-Muntahī*, a Sufi poetic work by Hamzah Fansuri.¹⁸ This manuscript comes from Banten in the 17th century and is written in prose, in *Pegon* script.¹⁹ The manuscript includes Arabic quotations that are then translated into Javanese, including the hadith “*al-insānu sirrī wa-anā sirruhu*”²⁰ (Man is My secret and I am its secret) and the wise words of a Sufi “*al-Ḥaqqu ‘aynu l-khalqī in kunta dhā ‘ayni wa-l-khalqu ghayru l-Ḥaqqī in kunta dhā ‘aqlī*” (God the Truth is the very essence of the creature if you are one with sight [a person who sees], the servant is not God the Truth if you are someone of reason).²¹ In both of these examples, there are several words that function as *mubtada'*: *al-insānu* (Man), *wa-anā* (and I), *al-Ḥaqqu* (God the Truth), and *wa-l-khalqu* (and the creature). However, of these four, only the *mubtada'* that follows *wāw* is translated with *utawi* (see the table below). Thus, *utawi* does not indicate the *mubtada'* but rather translates the *isti'nāf* function of *wāw*.

17 I classify the broader corpus into two script traditions: Javanese and *Pegon* scripts. The *Pegon* manuscripts can be further divided into those with and without interlinear translation. In the following two to three pages, I offer a brief and tentative observation on manuscripts outside my main corpus—namely, non-interlinear *Pegon* manuscripts and texts written in Javanese script.

18 Jan Just Witkam, *Inventory of the Oriental Manuscripts of the Library of the University of Leiden* (Ter Lugt Press, 2007), 6:194.

19 There is some disagreement about the dating of this manuscript, but I concur with Drewes, who follows Voorhoeve in assigning it to the 17th century Paul Voorhoeve, *Handlist of Arabic Manuscripts in the Library of the University of Leiden and Other Collections in the Netherlands* (Leiden University Press, 1980), 86. Drewes provides several reasons to support this dating, including the paper's watermark, the type of damage the paper has sustained, and the history of the reception of *al-Muntahī* in Banten, the manuscript's region of origin Drewes and Brakel, *The Poems of Hamzah Fansuri*, 251–52.

20 Drewes and Brakel, *The Poems of Hamzah Fansuri*, 269.

21 Drewes and Brakel, *The Poems of Hamzah Fansuri*, 257. English translations are mine. The English translations are deliberately kept as faithful as possible, in part to reproduce for the reader the riddle-like quality experienced by Javanese readers of the sentences.

<i>al-insānu</i>	<i>sirrī</i>	<i>wa-anā</i>	<i>sirruhu</i>
<i>manusia</i>	<i>iku rahsaningsun,</i>	<i>utawi ingsun</i>	<i>pun rahsane</i>
Man	is my secret	<i>utawi</i> I	am its secret
<i>al-ʔaqqu</i>	<i>ʔaynu l-khalqi</i>	<i>in kunta</i>	<i>dhā ʔayni</i>
<i>Kang Pangeran</i>	<i>iku kahananing kawula,</i>	<i>lamun sira</i>	<i>wong kang aningali</i>
God	is the state of the servant	if you are	a person who sees
<i>wa-l-khalqu</i>	<i>ghayru l-ʔaqqi</i>	<i>in kunta</i>	<i>dhā ʔaqli</i>
<i>Utawi kawula</i>	<i>iku liyan saking kahananing Pangeran</i>	<i>lamun ana sira</i>	<i>wong barbudi</i>
<i>Utawi</i> the servant	is other than [or is not] the state of God	if you are	a person of wisdom

Table 2 Line-by-line Javanese translation of Arabic quotations in Leiden UB Or. 5716.*

Further attestation can be found in another collection at the Leiden University Library. The manuscript with the code Or. 1928 is also known by the title used by Drewes in his translation of this manuscript, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari*.²² Originating from the northern coast of Java in the 16th century, this manuscript is a treatise on Islamic theology and Sufism, featuring Seh ul-Bari as a religious figure presenting the key teachings of Islam that form the content of the book.²³ In one of the discussions, there is a phrase “*utawi ana woñ sasar sawiji, Arabiyah arane, ak(e)cap*” (Or. 1928 fol. 27). This marks the beginning of a story about someone who, according to the author of this manuscript, does not practice Islam properly, thus becoming *sasar* (Jv. lost, gone astray). In telling this story, Or. 1928 is not translating from Arabic, making it an important example. While in the previous example we saw line-by-line translation (not word-for-word as in I F 31 and I H 1), here we encounter a stand-alone Javanese sentence whose construction follows a logic similar to that of interlinear translation.

The story of the person who went astray has been discussed by several scholars, resulting in various English translations of this expression. In his pioneering research, Drewes translated the sentence quite loosely as, “Another false doctrine is that of ‘Arabiyya (Ibn al-‘Arabi) who teaches as follows.”²⁴ However, I tend to agree with Yumi Sugahara’s more faithful translation, “There is another person who has lost his way. His name is ‘Arabiyya. He teaches as follows”, which allows us to better recognize the function of *utawi* in this sentence.²⁵ However, I must point out that even in Sugahara’s faithful translation, *utawi* is

22 Drewes, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari*.

23 Theodore G. Th. Pigeaud, *Literature of Java* (Martinus Nijhoff, 1968), 2:52.

24 Drewes, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari*, 59.

25 Yumi Sugahara, “Sunan Bonang’s Teaching: Ethical Sufism in Sixteenth-Century Java,” in *Storied Island: New Explorations in Javanese Literature*, ed. Ronit Ricci (Brill, 2023), 137.

not translated: “there is” translates *ana*, “another” likely translates *sawiji*, “person” translates *woñ*, “lost” translates *sasar*, and “who has” is an addition to make the English translation more readable, much like how *sawiji* (another) is moved to the beginning of the sentence this translation. I believe my argument about utawi as a rendering of wāw al-isti’nāf also applies here. Whether intentionally or not, by not translating utawi and capitalizing the letter T in “There,” Sugahara has preserved every word of the source text.²⁶

The final attestation comes from a manuscript in the collection of Thomas Erpenius, now housed in the Cambridge University Library. This manuscript bears a symbol indicating that before becoming part of Erpenius’ collection, it was owned by Josephus Scaliger, who passed away in 1609. In other words, this manuscript may have been written in the early 17th century or even the 16th century.²⁷ The manuscript with the code Gg.5.22 is a collection of several texts on Islamic theology and law (*fiqh*). In one section, there is an explanation of several theological and legal principles in Islam presented in the form of a catechisms with the formula *utawi lamun* (*utawi* if). This section spans several pages from fol. 114, and I will only highlight two examples.

On fol. 114, there is a catechism point: “*Utawi lamun sira tinakonan apa tegesing iman, sauranira, aneguhaken i barang kang den ucap, dene wo sawiji*” (*utawi* if you are asked what *īmān* means, reply “fulfilling what has been spoken, even if it’s just one thing”). On fol. 116: “*Utawi lamun sira tinakonan apa agama kang fardlu i syarang, sauranira agama ing Allah*” (*utawi* if you are asked which religion mandates the *sharī‘a*, reply “the religion of Allah”). In both of these examples, *utawi* is followed by *lamun*, which functions as a conditional particle, similar to *idhā* in the previous example. In this textual context, the appearance of *utawi* coincides with the beginning of a new catechism point—here, it resembles the appearance of *wāw* when it functions as *isti’nāf*.

The various examples of *utawi* usage discussed above suggest that, by the 17th century, there already existed an established interlinear translation system, to which the interlinear texts bear witness—a system that employed *utawi* to render wāw al-isti’nāf. In this system, *utawi* was also occasionally used to mark the *mubtada’* position but to a much lesser degree compared to its use for *isti’nāf*. This system seems to have been widely adopted and well-established, as evidenced by its use in Islamic manuscripts written in other formats, such as prose, during this period and probably the preceding century. However, several questions remain: When was this system first implemented? How did it become so influential and pervasive? In what circumstances and within what kinds of communities was it used? And how long did it remain in use? Unfortunately, the material evidence currently available to us does not allow for definitive answers to all of these questions—except, perhaps, the last one.

26 Another example of *utawi* as indicating a *mubtada’* can be found in this manuscript. In fol. 37, there is the phrase: “*Heh mitraniñsun, kalawan ta sira aja ña(m)bil dedeniñ woñ, utawi aja sira murtad iñ samitranira kañ asih iñ sira, kufur ukume,*” which Drewes translates as “My friends! Do not pay attention merely to people’s mistakes. Do not renounce your friends who are well-disposed towards you. That is unbelief.” Drewes, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari*, 67. Here, *utawi* also marks the beginning of a new discourse/point/sentence.

27 Majid Daneshgar, *Reconstructing Erpenius’ Library: The First Collection of Oriental Manuscripts at Cambridge University Library* (Brill, 2025), 61.

Utawi in Transition

Before continuing the discussion, I must clarify that all the manuscripts in the previous section are from the 17th century, or are presumed to be from that period. This section, however, focuses on manuscripts from the period leading into and throughout the 18th century, with occasional references to 19th-century materials. I should also note that I did not address the regional provenance of the manuscripts discussed earlier as the regional provenance of most of these manuscripts is unknown. For the sake of the argument I am proposing, I will take the same approach in this section, momentarily setting aside regional considerations. Therefore, anyone examining the regional aspect of these manuscripts and finding regional variations may and should revise and adjust this argument accordingly.

In this section, I explore the shifting use of utawi as documented in several 18th-century manuscripts. By “shifting,” I refer to the changing proportion between the use of utawi to render wāw al-isti’nāf and its use to mark the muftada’. While the former was clearly dominant in the 17th century, the pattern begins to reverse in the 18th. The manuscripts reveal a gradual shift: from the dominance of utawi-for-isti’nāf, to a more balanced usage, and eventually to the predominance of utawi as indicating the muftada’. They also show a growing complexity in how wāw al-isti’nāf and muftada’ are translated, especially when appearing with ḥarf or certain formulaic expressions. The following examples will help clarify these points.

The manuscript catalogued as A 45 in the collection of the National Library of the Republic of Indonesia (Perpustakaan Nasional Republik Indonesia, henceforth PNRI) is a composite manuscript. It comprises copies and interlinear translations of *Tuḥfat al-ṭālib al-muḥtadī wa-minḥat al-sālik al-muḥtadī* (fols. 1–142) and *Zubdat al-asrār* (fols. 153–385), along with various marginal and interstitial notes. Both works are attributed to Yūsuf Ṭāj al-Khalwatī al-Maqāṣirī (d. 1111/1699), although his name appears only in the copy of *Zubda*. This second work also includes a colophon—which the first text lacks—dating it to 1087 AH (1676 AD). However, as the colophon belongs to the source text, it cannot serve as direct evidence for dating the interlinear translation. At most, it provides a *terminus post quem* for its composition. I will return to this issue of dating in the following section; here, I focus on the use of utawi in this manuscript.

In this manuscript and the following examples, I will examine the use and absence of utawi across three categories: (1) muftada’ preceded by wāw al-isti’nāf, (2) muftada’ not preceded by wāw al-isti’nāf, and (3) wāw al-isti’nāf followed by fi’l or ḥarf. In this particular manuscript, utawi is most frequently used to translate cases in the first category and appears much less often in the second and third. While there are always some instances where the translation occurs without utawi in all the categories, it is most notably absent in the translation of the second. Interestingly, some verbs (*fi’l*) are translated with utawi even when they are not preceded by wāw al-isti’nāf, as shown in the case of *i’lam* (imperative, “know!” or “be aware!”) in Fig. 5. A likely explanation for this is that *i’lam* often appears elsewhere in the text preceded by and is regularly translated with utawi. Thus, it can be inferred that the utawi-for-isti’nāf pattern remains dominant in this manuscript.

Fig. 6 *Tuhfat al-tālib al-mubtadī*, The National Library of Indonesia, A 45, fol. 157. The formulaic translation of the pronoun *hiya* and the use of *utawi* for neither *wāw al-isti'nāf* nor *mubtada'*.

There are several intriguing points worth noting. The exceptions observed in the three earlier interlinear manuscripts regarding the translation of pronouns *huwa* (he) and *hiya* (she), as well as instances where *fa-* (then) interrupts the structure of *wāw al-isti'nāf* and *mubtada'*, also appear in this manuscript, albeit with even greater consistency. In cases where *huwa* and *hiya* occupy the grammatical position of *mubtada'*, with or without *wāw* (whether functioning as *isti'nāf* or as a conjunction), they are invariably translated in a formulaic manner as *lan iya iku* (and it is) (as shown in Fig. 5). A new exception I identified in this manuscript pertains to the translation of ordinal numbers (e.g., *awwal/ūlā* for “first,” *thānī* for “second,” *thālith* for “third,” etc.). In this manuscript these terms are never translated with *utawi*, or, if *utawi* is used, it only appears for *awwal/ūlā* and is not used for subsequent ordinals. All of this, in my view, reinforces the previous conclusion that the *utawi-for-isti'nāf* pattern remains dominant in manuscripts from the third quarter of the 17th century.

As the century drew to a close, the pattern of *utawi* usage appears to have undergone a shift. This transition is evident in the composite manuscript A 97 from the collection of the National Library of Indonesia. Written in or after 1100/1688, this manuscript employs *utawi* to translate *wāw al-isti'nāf* (including instances where it is followed by *ḥarf*), but it predominantly uses *utawi* to render the *mubtada'*.²⁸ Notably, the phrase *wa-lam*, which is frequently translated with *utawi* even when *wāw al-isti'nāf* is absent (as seen in A 45), is never rendered as *utawi* in this manuscript; it only has *lan* (and). Likewise, *wa-ammā*, a

28 On the first page of the manuscript, there is an ownership statement that mentions the year of its composition, although it is unfortunately incomplete. The statement reads: “*Sharaḥ Tuhfa Mawāhib al-Mursala kalaning sinerat sasi Jumadil Akhir tanggal ping roliku(r) tahun zā(y) ... nabi ṣal'am [sic.] ... sewu satu(s) ... lemampah?*” (Supercommentary on *Tuhfa*, the *Mawāhib al-Mursala*, written in the month of *Jumādā al-Ākhir*, the twenty-second, year *zāy* ... the Prophet *ṣal'am* ... one thousand and one hundred ... has passed). The letters in brackets indicate they are missing. I have left gaps in some places to account for the words that should have appeared but are cut off. This note indicates that the manuscript was written in or after the year 1100 AH, corresponding to approximately 1688 AD.

commonly occurring phrase, is no longer translated with *utawi* as it typically is. This suggests a discernible shift, with the use of *utawi* to translate the *mubtada'* becoming increasingly dominant.

The dominance of *utawi-for-mubtada'* appears to have remained relatively stable until the first quarter of the 18th century, as evidenced in the manuscript Or. 5675 from the Leiden University Library. This manuscript, dated 1142 AH (1729–30 AD), consistently translates the *mubtada'* with or without *wāw al-isti'nāf* using *utawi*. Although there are a few instances where the *mubtada'* is translated without *utawi*, these occurrences are sufficiently rare and can be regarded as human errors. The translations of *huwalhiya*, *wa-ammā*, *fa-ammā*, and *wa-'lam* remain consistently without *utawi*, reflecting the same pattern observed in the PNRI A 97 manuscript. Of particular note in Or. 5675 is the complete absence of instances where *wāw al-isti'nāf*, followed by *fi'l* or *ḥarf*, are translated with *utawi*. This suggests the dominance of *utawi-for-mubtada'*. Nevertheless, this manuscript does not signify the end of the use of *utawi-for-isti'nāf*. Another Leiden collection, Or. 1842, which includes colophons dating from 1168/1754-5 and 1186/1772-3, offers important evidence for that. In this manuscript we observe the same general pattern of *utawi* usage with a continued dominance of *utawi-for-mubtada'*. Yet, *utawi* continues to appear in the translation of *wāw al-isti'nāf* followed by *fi'l* and *ḥarf*, albeit with considerably lower frequency.²⁹

Fig. 7 An untitled tract from al-Rifā'ī order, Leiden University Library, Or. 1842, fol. 346r. The use of *utawi* to translate *wāw al-isti'nāf* followed by a *fi'l*.

²⁹ Another example is found in fol. 336v, where *wa-yajibu* (and it is mandatory) is translated as *utawi wajib* (*utawi* mandatory). Additionally, an interesting case of translation variation appears on fol. 106r, where two instances of *wa-mā*—where *mā* functions as a *ḥarf nafi* (negative particle)—are translated differently, offering an intriguing example of *ḥarf* usage. In this instance, the first *wa-mā* appears in *wa-mā mashā aḥad* (and no one is walking) and translates to *utawi oratah lumaku wong sawiji* (*utawi* someone is not walking). The second *wa-mā* appears in *wa-mā awā aḥad* (and no one is going down) and translates to *lan ora tumurun wong sawiji* (and someone is not going down). The use of *utawi* and *lan* may indicate the translator's different understandings of the two instances of *wa-mā*: the first as *isti'nāf*, thus rendered with *utawi*, and the second as *'ataf* (conjunction), rendered with *lan*.

The manuscripts reveal a gradual shift in the dominant usage of utawi from translating wāw al-isti'nāf to translating muftada'. This transition is marked by several observable symptoms, two of the most notable being the increasing frequency with which utawi is used to translate muftada' without a preceding wāw al-isti'nāf and the absence of utawi in rendering wāw al-isti'nāf followed by a fi'l or ḥarf. This shift is clearly evident in manuscript PNRI A 97, dating from the last quarter of the 17th century, and becomes more pronounced in Leiden Or. 5675 from the first quarter of the 18th century.

The increasing dominance is further observed in Leiden Or. 1842, from the second and third quarters of the 18th century, where the dominance of utawi-for-muftada' is firmly established. However, even within this pattern, utawi-for-isti'nāf has not been entirely supplanted. While instances of utawi-for-isti'nāf become increasingly subtle, a careful reader can still discern their presence. The dominance of utawi-for-muftada' and the subtle appearance of utawi-for-isti'nāf continued well into the 19th century (Fig. 8a and 8b). The older form *utawi anapun* for *wa-ammā* appears to have persisted, likely because it did not entirely conflict with the utawi-for-muftada' structure, given that the word following *wa-ammā* in many instances is a noun functioning as a muftada'.

Fig. 8a An untitled work on Islamic theology, Endangered Archives Programme British Library, EAP061/2/34, fol. 75v. The use of utawi to translate wāw al-isti'nāf plus ḥarf in a 19th-century manuscript.

Fig. 8b An untitled work on Islamic theology, Endangered Archives Programme British Library, EAP061/2/34, fol. 75v. The use of utawi to translate wāw al-isti'nāf plus fi'l in a 19th-century manuscript.

These compelling findings lead to several critical questions that require extensive evidence and further contextual understanding to be addressed thoroughly. How should we interpret this shift in usage? Does it represent a change in emphasis, and if so, what were the underlying reasons? What specific factors in the 18th century contributed to this transition? Is this shift the only significant one within this period, or are there other notable transitions to be considered? If other shifts did occur in subsequent periods, what factors might have driven them? Are the factors influencing the shift in utawi usage the same as those influencing other changes? Do these transitions provide insights into a broader historical, intellectual, or cultural transformation, such as the evolving orientation of Javanese Islamic identity?

Utawi as a Dating Device?

Although these questions remain a mystery and will likely require considerable time before we can provide solid answers, the shift in the use of utawi offers valuable insights for philologists and historians in various ways, one among them being the consideration of manuscripts' dating. Insights emerging from scholarly exchanges I have had with experts in Islamic manuscript traditions in Java suggest that the better we understand the nature and system of Javanese interlinear translation, the more we are able to approximate the regional provenance and dating of an anonymous and undated manuscript. The evidence presented above suggests a clearer understanding of the function of utawi and in this section, I offer several case studies that demonstrate how utawi can be used as a tool for dating interlinear manuscripts.

The manuscript in the Leiden collection, coded Or. 7165, presents an intriguing case given the rarity of its interlinear translation. It is a composite manuscript, believed by Voorhoeve to have been written in the 17th century. Characterized by relatively wide spacing and only rare occasional, sporadic interlinear translation, this manuscript poses particular challenges for dating attempts that rely on utawi as an analytical device. Can we hope to date a manuscript that features so few interlinear translations? Let us give it a try. In the instances where interlinear translations do appear, utawi is used multiple times, and interestingly, quite a few instances of utawi translate a wāw al-isti'nāf followed by a verb or particle. The manuscript never uses utawi to indicate the position of the mubtada', which serves as an important clue. When placed within the pattern observed in the previous sections, this provides further support for the hypothesis that this manuscript was written in the 17th century. Furthermore, the word translated as utawi is the famous phrase *wa-'lam* (know!), which, in 17th-century manuscripts like PNRI A 45, receives utawi without the need for the wāw al-isti'nāf.

Fig. 9 *Al-Miṣbāḥ fī al-Naḥw*, Leiden University Library, Or. 7165, a composite text, fol. 11r. The use of utawi to translate wāw al-isti'nāf followed by the verb *i'lam*.

In the previous section, I discussed the dating issue of PNRI A 45. The year 1087 AH (1676 AD), mentioned in the manuscript's colophon, is part of the source text and, therefore, cannot be directly used to establish the date of the interlinear translation. This date should be regarded only as a *terminus post quem* for the translation's composition. Nevertheless, within this manuscript, utawi remains predominantly employed to translate wāw al-isti'nāf. Words functioning as mubtada' that are not preceded by wāw al-isti'nāf are frequently translated without utawi. Furthermore, the manuscript presents a notable instance where the verb *i'lam* is translated with utawi, despite the absence of wāw al-isti'nāf preceding it. In essence, the use of utawi for wāw al-isti'nāf holds a dominant position in this text. All of this indicates the characteristic usage of utawi in the 17th century and earlier. Had this manuscript been written in the 18th century or later, one would anticipate a greater prevalence of utawi used to translate the mubtada'. Thus, while the date 1087/1676 cannot serve as the definitive year for the interlinear translation's composition, the usage of utawi helps to narrow the translation's period of creation to a window spanning from 1087/1676 to the early 18th century.

Another example is PNRI A 54 and the manuscript from the Great Banten Mosque (Masjid Agung Banten, henceforth MAB 1). Both are Javanese Quran translations from Banten—A 54 was originally housed in the royal palace before being transferred to the Bataviaasch Genootschap (the precursor to the PNRI), while MAB 1, as the name suggests, belongs to the collection of Masjid Agung Banten. They are believed to be complete translations of the Quran, although today we no longer have access to the entire translated text. PNRI A 54 is missing the 15th and 16th *juz*'s (parts), while MAB 1 retains only the translation of the last 10 *juz*' (21-30). Both are undated; however, scholars speculate that PNRI A 54 dates from the 18th century, while local oral tradition holds that MAB 1 was written a century earlier. Does the use of utawi support or challenge these chronological assumptions?

Fig. 10 Quran with Javanese interlinear translation, The National Library of Indonesia, A 54 a, fol. 5. The use of utawi to translate wāw al-isti'nāf followed by the ḥarf *min*.

In PNRI A 54, utawi is used to translate words in the position of the *mubtada*'³⁰. However, when this *mubtada*' is preceded by *fā*, utawi is replaced by *maka* or is omitted altogether.³⁰ The same applies to *fa-ammā*, whereas *wa-ammā* is always translated as *lan anapun* instead of *utawi anapun*. The pronouns *huwa* (he) and *hiya* (she) are translated as *iya iku* and take the addition of *lan* (and) when preceded by wāw al-isti'nāf. However, most notably, utawi is still used to translate wāw al-isti'nāf followed by a ḥarf (Fig. 11).³¹ This pattern is also found in MAB 1, with the exception of the latter. In MAB 1, I did not find utawi used to translate wāw al-isti'nāf followed by either ḥarf or *fīl*. In other words, the use of utawi in both manuscripts strengthens the assumption that PNRI A 54 dates from the 18th century, but does not support (and may even weaken) the assumption that MAB 1 originates from the 17th century. The latter may be an exception to the rule or rather date from the late 18th century or later.

Certainly, looking at the usage of utawi alone cannot serve as a decisive method for dating a manuscript. However, the key point I wish to make is that a deeper understanding of the

30 For example, the translation of *fa-Allāhu khayrun ḥifẓan* in Q. 12:64 as *maka Allah iku lewih becik pangreksane* (then Allah is the one whose surveillance is better) (PNRI A 54c, fol. 5).

31 In the course of my investigation, I have not encountered any instance in this manuscript where utawi is used to translate a wāw al-isti'nāf followed by a *fīl*.

characteristics of interlinear translation can offer valuable clues or reinforce hypotheses regarding the dating of a manuscript. If one delves deeper into the various code words used in Javanese interlinear translations, beyond just *utawi*, much more can be uncovered, far beyond dating. *Utawi* is a gateway to a rich and beautiful tropical rainforest of knowledge.

Conclusion

Throughout this article, I have explored the use of the word *utawi* in early Islamic literature in Java, mostly within interlinear translation texts. In modern usage, *utawi* is primarily employed to denote a word in the position of the nominal sentence's subject, the *mubtada'*. However, when examined diachronically, starting from the earliest available manuscripts—dating back to the 16th century—it becomes apparent that *utawi*'s role underwent notable change. In the 16th and 17th centuries, *utawi* primarily served as a translation for the *isti'nāf* function of the Arabic particle *wāw*. Only in a limited number of cases did it signify the *mubtada'* of a translated phrase. This usage pattern does, however, include exceptions for certain words, such as the pronouns *huwa-hiya* (he-she) and ordinal numbers like *awwal-thānī-thālith* (first-second-third). Moreover, the translation of *utawi* was subject to variation when faced with *fa* (then). Nonetheless, in this early period, *utawi* was predominantly employed to translate the *isti'nāf* function, rather than serving to indicate the *mubtada'*.

As time went on, the use of *utawi* to mark the *mubtada'* became increasingly prominent, while its earlier function as a rendering of *wāw al-isti'nāf* gradually receded. This shift is clearly observable in 18th-century manuscripts, where *utawi-for-mubtada'* gains stability toward century's end, and instances of *utawi-for-isti'nāf* become markedly infrequent. Exceptions to this pattern—such as its use with certain pronouns or after specific particles—also show signs of consolidation, further reinforcing *utawi-for-mubtada'* as the prevailing norm. Yet, traces of its former function as a marker of *isti'nāf* persisted well into the 19th century, and as of writing this study, I have yet to identify the precise point at which that function disappeared altogether. Although much remains to be explored about the historical trajectory of *utawi*, the patterns that have emerged thus far offer a useful framework for various lines of inquiry, chief among them the dating of manuscripts. As demonstrated in the final section, patterns in *utawi* usage often align with other manuscript features that can help suggest a likely date of origin.

By outlining these findings, I hope to invite readers to reassess and deepen their understanding of the Javanese interlinear translation system, particularly as it appears in manuscripts from the formative period of Javanese Islam (the 16th-18th centuries). Just as *utawi*—whose partial “life history” I have attempted to trace here—underwent a historical evolution, other elements of the *utawi-iku* translation system must have followed their own developmental paths. Some may have assumed stable functions from the outset, while others likely experienced gradual yet meaningful transitions, as *utawi* did.

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Manuscripts

Interlinear manuscripts

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2. Library of the University of Amsterdam, I H 1, *al-Īdāh*, regional provenance unknown, *terminus ante quem* 1610.
3. The British Museum Library, Sloane 2645, *al-Muqaddima al-Ḥadrāmiyya*, regional provenance unknown, colophon bringing the year 1545 AJ (Anno Javanese) = 1623 AD.
4. Leiden University Library, Or. 7165, *al-Miṣbāh fī al-Nahw*, regional provenance unknown, supposedly from the 17th century.
5. Perpustakaan Nasional Republik Indonesia, A 45, *Tuḥfat al-Ṭālib al-Mubtadī*, copied in Banten 1087/1676.
6. Perpustakaan Nasional Republik Indonesia, A 97, *al-Mawāhib al-Mursala*, copied in Banten in 1116/1705.
7. Leiden University Library, Or. 2016, composite manuscript on theology and sufism, copied in 18th-century Banten.
8. Leiden University Library, Or. 5675, *Mashra‘ al-Khuṣūṣ ilā Ma‘ānī al-Nuṣūṣ*, copied in Banten in 1142/1729-30.
9. Perpustakaan Nasional Republik Indonesia, A 34, *al-Fayḍ al-‘Ahd fī al-‘Ilm bi-‘Uluww al-Sanaad*, copied in Banten in 1174/1760-1.
10. Leiden University Library, Or. 1842, composite manuscript containing varying works on sufism, supposedly copied in Banten in the second half of the 18th century.
11. Endangered Archives Programme British Library, EAP061/2/34, untitled work on Islamic theology, copied in Lamongan, East Java, supposedly in the 19th century.

Non-interlinear manuscripts in *Pegon*

1. Leiden University Library, Or. 5716, *al-Muntahī*, probably from 17th-century Banten.
2. Leiden University Library, Or. 3050, untitled work on Islamic theology and sufism, regional provenance unknown, hypothetically Kudus, Central Java, 17th century.

Non-interlinear manuscripts in Javanese script

1. Leiden University Library, Or. 1928, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari*, 16th century, probably from Tuban, East Java.
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